

COLD-WORKING AND MELT PROCESSING INTERFACES ON SILVER/HIGH TEMPERATURE SUPERCONDUCTOR COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The interfaces of two textured Ag/Bi-Sr-Ca-Cu-O high temperature superconducting ceramic composites have been studied and compared. Melt textured fibres were obtained using the Laser Floating Zone (LFZ) method. Silver sheathed composite tapes were obtained using the Powder in Tube method, followed by rolling and axial pressing. A microstructure analysis of texture and the Ag interface has been carried out using electronic (SEM and TEM with EDS), as well as polarised optical microscopies.

Keywords: high T_c superconductors; Ag/Bi 2223 tapes and fibres.

1. INTRODUCTION

Textured High Temperature Superconducting Ceramics (HTSC) are extremely important for the development of practical superconducting devices based on these new materials. The development of conductors with very high critical current densities (J_c values greater than 1×10^4 A cm⁻²) without losses in the presence of magnetic fields ($B = 0.1$ or 1 T depending on their potential applications) and working at 77 K (liquid nitrogen) or lower temperatures is one of the present goals. In addition, the use of metal/superconductor composites would be desirable, since the metal matrix could provide improved mechanical, thermal and chemical stability and a low resistance electrical pathway in case of superconductor failure, thus avoiding the development of irreversibly damaging hot spots. Furthermore, these composites would make low resistance connections possible.

The most promising results towards practical cables have so far been obtained with the Powder-in-Tube (PIT) method on silver sheathed Bi-Sr-Ca-Cu-O (BSCCO) materials.^[1] Because of the plasticity of the BSCCO phases, the combination of drawing and lamination (rolling/pressing) and annealing cycles,^[2] have yielded laminated composites in the form of tapes with $J_c > 5.4 \times 10^4$ A cm⁻² at 77 K and $B = 0$ T.^[3]

In this contribution two alternative processing methods have been used to obtain Ag/BSCCO textured composites: i) the Laser Floating Zone (LFZ) method, which allows to grow these composites from the melt in the form of thick fibres,^[4,5] and ii) the above mentioned PIT method.^[1,2,6] Polarised optical and scanning electron microscopy, implemented with energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM-EDS), permitted a comparative analysis of the microstructure.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was used to study Ag/BSCCO interfaces. These microstructural features were correlated with the composite fibres' and tapes' macroscopic properties.

2. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

During LFZ processing, previously well-characterised Ag/BSCCO ceramic precursors were melted with the use of a CO₂ laser and directionally solidified in air with the aid of a superconductor seed. The Ag and BSCCO form an eutectic in which silver, superconducting phases and other oxides solidify separately giving well aligned BSCCO grains with the *c*-axis perpendicular to the growth direction are found, and the (*a-b*) plane oriented at random. Very thin flat parallel grains ($\approx 50\text{-}100\text{ nm}$) form thicker blocks or agglomerates ($\approx 1\text{-}5\ \mu\text{m}$) of various lengths ($200\text{-}500\ \mu\text{m}$) which have been observed in pure fibres.^[7] This values, however, change widely depending on the ceramic precursor stoichiometry and on the growth conditions. As may be seen in the optical and SEM micrograph of Fig. 1, in addition to the expected lamellar or fibre structure, the silver tends to crystallise with a dendritic habit extending along the growth axis, but without connectivity between the grains as determined by TEM studies. Furthermore, the Ag dendrites sometimes also form a pattern in the perpendicular direction. For the silver concentrations studied (lower than 30% wt. in the starting ceramic precursor), the distribution of Ag in a cross-section is not uniform. The silver precipitates tend to concentrate towards the fibre's edge, leaving the fibre's centre with a much lower silver concentration. SEM(EDS) analyses have proven that there is no Ag outside of the above mentioned precipitates, discarding the presence of significant Ag diffusion into the oxide phases identified in the fibres. The presence of silver does not disturb the intrinsic superconducting properties of the material and, as no changes are observed in the diamagnetic onset temperature T_c or in the magnetic properties of the fibres at high fields. Moreover, the fibres' J_c values are observed to increase with the presence of Ag at low concentration levels.

Fig. 1a Optical polarised micrograph of a Ag/BSCCO composite fibre showing the dendritic structure of Ag (polished sample).

Fig. 1b Detail obtained with SEM of Ag dendrites on the polished surface of the fibre. Ca-Sr-Cu oxides appear as dark areas and grey areas correspond to BSCCO grains.

For PIT processing, well characterised pure BSCCO and Ag/BSCCO powders (monofilamentary wires) as well as thinner composite wires^[8] (multifilamentary wires) were densely packed into a silver tube, drawn into small diameter wire, and laminated into a tape by rolling and pressing procedures followed by annealing. After optimisation, the ceramic core contained highly aligned BSCCO grains with the (*a-b*) plane parallel to the tape's surface. Apparently there is no diffusion of Ag into BSCCO, and the nature of the interface is not known. A SEM image of the polished cross-section of an optimised tape, with $J_c = 31000 \text{ A cm}^{-2}$ at 77 K in zero field is shown in Fig. 2. The long (10-30 μm) and thin (<100 nm) BSCCO grains also form thicker agglomerates parallel to the silver sheath. Most of these appear bent at small angles and sometimes mechanical deformation induced high angle bending. Grain parallelism decreases towards the tape's centre where secondary phases precipitate disturbing the alignment of the more plastic, surrounding BSCCO phases.

Fig. 2 SEM micrograph (backscattered electrons on polished sample) of a silver sheathed Ag/BSCCO monofilamentary tape.

For a given stoichiometry, the size of the precipitates depends on grain size and morphology in the starting powder. The synthetic methods employed^[9] may change thereafter the overall grain alignment and thus the final J_c values. In tapes prepared using Ag-containing starting powders, the silver concentrates in flat grains (5-10 μm wide) which appear sandwiched between BSCCO aggregates^[10] determining their morphology. The Ag/BSCCO interface exhibits the highest degree of texture observed; the addition of Ag would thus increase the interface area. Therefore, as in the case of the fibres, the presence of Ag does not disturb the intrinsic superconducting properties of the grains, while it increases the J_c performance.^[2,10]

In both cases, as grown materials (fibres and tapes) required annealing in order to adjust the oxygen content and/or to heal cracks, to improve their superconducting properties. In BSCCO systems there are two superconducting phases of technological interest with nominal compositions $\text{Bi}_2\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{10.8}$ (2223), with $T_c \approx 110$ K and $\text{Bi}_2\text{Sr}_2\text{CaCu}_2\text{O}_{10.8}$ (2212) with $T_c \approx 80$ K. To enlarge the temperature range of potential applications, it would be desirable to have materials with the pure 2223 phase. This is facilitated using lead doping, where Bi is partially substituted by Pb ($\text{Bi}_{1.8}\text{Pb}_{0.2}$). However, even in the best cases, the 2223 phase always coexists with the 2212 and/or other non superconducting phases belonging to the SrO-CaO-CuO ternary system.

3. DISCUSSION

The role of the silver either facilitating the electrical contact between grains, avoiding the propagation of cracks or enhancing texture (which would increase J_c in tapes) is not yet understood.^[2] Arguments may be found for and against the presence of a transient liquid in the tapes containing Ag as constituent ^[2,11] To give some insight on the problem, a study using electron microscopy techniques has been performed for both types of textured composites.

In the composite fibres, as well as in the best tapes, a majority of the 2223 phase grains tend to be in contact with silver by means of (001) planes. The tetragonal habit of the BSCCO grains in both kinds of samples, induced by directional solidification in LFZ fibres or by rolling-pressing-annealing processing in tapes, results in flat grains displaying (001) planes as the main contact surface with the silver or with other BSCCO grains. In this way, a sharp interface has been reported in silver sheathed tapes between the (001) BSCCO planes and the silver sheath.^[11,12] A SEM micrograph of the Ag/BSCCO interface area of a tape is shown in Fig. 3, where the plastic deformation of the BSCCO grains can be clearly observed. For larger quantities of secondary phases in the tape (mainly Ca-Sr-Cu and Cu oxides), increased irregularities are observed at the ceramic silver interface, because these phases do not undergo plastic deformation as easily as BSCCO grains.^[9] Moreover, when these precipitates are in the border of the ceramic core they may disturb the Ag/(001) parallelism, although they appear generally surrounded by flat BSCCO grains.

TEM images of the two types of Ag/BSCCO interfaces found in composite fibres are shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 4a shows a sharp interface (the same observed in silver sheathed tapes) without perturbation caused by Ag diffusion, whose habit does not seem to play any important role in inducing texture. However, 40-50 nm thick amorphous interfaces (determined by convergent beam electron diffraction) between (001) oriented BSCCO grains and the silver grain, as the one showed in Fig. 4b, have been found in the fibres. No abnormal concentration of any element of the BSCCO series has been detected using TEM-EDS on this amorphous zone. The nature and origin of this kind of interface has not yet been properly established. Moreover, an intimate mixture of 2223 and 2212 phases evolving with the annealing is also observed.

Fig. 3 SEM micrograph (backscattered electrons on polished sample) showing the Ag/BSCCO interface in a tape.

Fig. 4 TEM micrographs of the Ag/BSCCO interface in a composite fibre (20% wt. Ag). In Fig. 4a a sharp interface is shown and in Fig. 4b an amorphous zone between the Ag and BSCCO grains is shown. In both cases the interface is parallel to the (001) BSCCO planes observed in these high resolution micrographs.

The separate solidification of the Ag and BSCCO phases, together with the higher melting temperature and thermal conductivity of silver may explain the appearance of dendrites in the fibres. In agreement with concepts discussed for directionally solidified ceramic eutectics^[13], constitutional supercooling occurs when grains of the solid can nucleate in the melt ahead of the solid-liquid interface, resulting in the equiaxed randomly oriented dendritic microstructure observed in these LFZ fibres. On the other hand, lamellar growth of the BSCCO phase, Ag and secondary oxides is also produced due to the high axial thermal gradients characteristic to LFZ processing. In this case the growth of BSCCO, however, takes place usually through crystallographic (001) planes, although in some cases a thin amorphous buffer interlayer appears between the superconductor and silver grains.

There is an important difference in the texture of fibres and tapes. In the former, the BSCCO grains quite often have high c-axis angle intergranular junctions, forming prismatic volumes and open channels where Ag and other secondary non-superconducting phases accumulate. In contrast, the c-axis mis-alignment of neighbouring grains in tapes is smaller. Correspondingly, the J_c values found so far in tapes is between one and two orders of magnitude higher than in fibres.

4. CONCLUSIONS

No evidence of chemical interaction between Ag and BSCCO phases could be detected in both melt and cold-worked textured composites. Sharply defined surfaces of the superconductor grains with the (001) planes in contact with the silver are observed in tapes and fibres. In some cases, however, TEM studies performed on fibres reveal also the presence of amorphous thin interfaces (40-50 nm) between silver and BSCCO grains, having the stoichiometry of the latter. Moreover, the melt process yields other interfaces in the fibres, exemplified by the interfaces found around the Ag dendrites.

In the tapes, the silver forms interfaces mainly with BSCCO phases, whereas the nonsuperconducting secondary phase precipitates, which are surrounded by BSCCO, are generally inside the ceramic core. The lack of dendrites and other phenomena characteristic of the melt processed samples in the tapes, points towards the absence of significant amounts of a constituent Ag-containing liquid.

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